

The scanning law for GAIA

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1 Introduction

This note provides a summary of the rationale for the revolving scanning law and discusses the conditions for good sky coverage. Although most of this was completely worked out in the early phases of the Hipparcos project, much of it was forgotten once the Hipparcos scanning law had been fixed, and the GAIA community may be unfamiliar with some important considerations. (The revolving scanning was proposed for Hipparcos in 1976 by E. Høg, who subsequently worked out the basic conditions for good sky coverage and ‘uniform revolving scanning’.)

Most generally the scanning law is a prescription for the celestial coordinates of the spin ($\mathbf{z}$) axis as a function of time, plus a prescription about the spin motion about that axis (which may or may not be coupled to the first prescription). It is convenient to use ecliptic coordinates, so that the first prescription defines the functions $\lambda_z(t)$ and $\beta_z(t)$. We will leave the second prescription undefined for the moment, except to say that it should probably correspond as close as possible to an inertially constant rotation rate.

The measurement principle of Hipparcos or GAIA requires that the astrometric parameters (position, parallax and proper motion) of a star located anywhere on the sky can be recovered from a series of one-dimensional angular measurements, roughly along great-circle arcs, distributed over a few successive years. This requirement can be expressed very precisely in terms of the conditioning of the observation equations for the astrometric parameters, as a function of position on the sky, which can be calculated for any given functions $\lambda_z(t)$ and $\beta_z(t)$. However, for a *general* optimisation of the scanning law this is not very helpful, as the set of possible such functions is practically infinite. Instead, one must rely on a reasoning based on the most important characteristics of the scanning. We shall see that this leads to the conclusion that a ‘uniform revolving scanning law’ is likely to be optimal for this kind of mission.

2 Why revolving scanning?

Consider a great-circle scan for which the spin axis is fixed at $\mathbf{z}$, the sun is at $\mathbf{s}$, and the star is at $\mathbf{a}$ (Figure 1). The scan is perpendicular to the arc through $\mathbf{z}$ and $\mathbf{a}$, and the angle $\widehat{\mathbf{z}\mathbf{a}}$ must be close to 90° for the star to appear in the field of view at some time during the spin. Let ξ , θ , ψ and η be angles in the spherical triangle $\mathbf{z}\mathbf{s}\mathbf{a}$ as in the figure. If ϖ is the parallax of the star at $\mathbf{a}$, then its satellitocentric position is displaced towards the sun (i.e. along the great-circle arc from $\mathbf{a}$ to $\mathbf{s}$) by the angle $\Delta = \varpi \sin \theta$, assuming the satellite to be at 1 AU distance from the sun. However, the one-dimensional measurement is only

sensitive to the displacement *along* the scan, i.e. to $\Delta \times \sin \eta$. Using the sine theorem we have

$$\Delta \times \sin \eta = \varpi \sin \xi \sin \psi. \quad (1)$$

This formula is fundamental for the parallax measurement capability of GAIA. The (absolute) parallax ϖ is obtained by observing the same star $\mathbf{a}$ under different geometrical configurations in which the parallax factor $\sin \xi \sin \psi$ takes different values. The greater the variation of this factor is, the better the parallax will be determined. Obviously the factor $\sin \psi$ may span the full interval $[-1, +1]$ provided that $\mathbf{z}$ is at least sometimes on either side of the sun, as viewed from $\mathbf{a}$. For this to hold for any point $\mathbf{a}$ on the sky requires that $\mathbf{z}$, in the course of the scanning law, occupies many different points around $\mathbf{s}$. Since the parallax factor is also proportional to $\sin \xi$, the angle ξ should in principle be as close to 90° as possible (although $\xi = 90^\circ$ would mean scanning through the sun, which is of course undesirable).

In practice thermal/optical shielding and power requirements set an upper limit on ξ at $50\text{--}60^\circ$ (the case $\xi > 90^\circ$ corresponds to retrograde spin, which for symmetry reasons need not be considered). Given such a ‘hard’ limit, it is obvious that the best policy, from the viewpoint of parallax accuracy, is to keep ξ fixed at its maximum possible value.

Given a fixed angle ξ it follows that $\mathbf{z}$ will always be located on a small circle of radius ξ around the sun. Given, furthermore, that $\sin \psi$ should attain its extreme values with approximately the same probability for any point $\mathbf{a}$ (a reasonable requirement for good sky uniformity), it follows that $\mathbf{z}$ should be approximately uniformly distributed along the small circle. If we finally assume that (large) discontinuities in $\lambda_z(t)$ and $\beta_z(t)$ are undesirable from an operational point of view, the only reasonable solution is to make $\mathbf{z}$ describe a precessional motion (continuous or in small steps) around the solar direction, i.e. a revolving scanning. Having fixed the ‘revolving angle’ ξ it is now only necessary to specify the ‘revolving phase’ $\nu(t)$ (Figure 2), since

$$\lambda_z(t) = \lambda_s(t) + \arctan[\tan \xi \cos \nu(t)], \quad (2)$$

$$\beta_z(t) = \arcsin[\sin \xi \sin \nu(t)]. \quad (3)$$

$\lambda_s(t)$, the longitude of the sun as function of time, is of course fixed by Nature. (We assume that $\beta_s = 0$.) With $\nu(t)$ increasing more or less linearly with time, the path of $\mathbf{z}$ describes loops around the sun as in Figures 3 and 4. The two most important parameters of this scanning law are ξ and K , the number of loops per year; the latter is defined more precisely as the time average

$$K = \left\langle \frac{d\nu}{d\lambda_s} \right\rangle. \quad (4)$$

In principle K may be negative as well as positive, but for reasons of symmetry nothing is lost (at least in the present considerations) by restricting to the case $K > 0$.

3 Conditions for good sky coverage

In Figure 1 the object $\mathbf{a}$ will be scanned (i.e. go through the field of view) if and only if the angle $\widehat{\mathbf{z}\mathbf{a}}$ differs from 90° by less than half the width of the field of view. Conversely,

in Figure 3, the point $\mathbf{a}$ may be scanned at the times when the spin axis is approximately at $\mathbf{z}_1$, $\mathbf{z}_2$, and $\mathbf{z}_3$, i.e. at the intersections of the $\mathbf{z}$ path with the great circle (A) having its pole at $\mathbf{a}$. Whether it is actually scanned at all three times depends on the speed of $\mathbf{z}$ along its path, and the phase of the spin at these times. However, there is a simple way to ensure that $\mathbf{a}$ will be scanned at least once at each of the three occasions, viz. if the speed of $\mathbf{z}$ on the sky is less than the width of the field of view per spin period, or:

$$|\dot{\mathbf{z}}| \leq \frac{W\omega}{2\pi}. \quad (5)$$

Here $\dot{\mathbf{z}} = d\mathbf{z}/dt$, W is the width of the field of view, and ω is the scan speed in rad s^{-1} . If this condition is met, and the loops overlap as in Figure 3, we see that *any* point on the sky will be scanned at least three times per semester (six times per year). Moreover, it can be seen that some of the scans (such as those at $\mathbf{z}_2$ and $\mathbf{z}_3$) will be made with the $\sin\psi$ factor not far from its extreme values ± 1 , as required for good parallax determinations. The scans are also somewhat spread out in time, with a minimum separation of about $1/K$ year between the first and last observation in a group such as $\mathbf{z}_1$, $\mathbf{z}_2$, $\mathbf{z}_3$, and the directions of the scans across $\mathbf{a}$ differ by an angle which is at least about 2ξ ; both of these properties improve the separation of the astrometric parameters and the ability to detect and correctly treat more complex or variable objects.

The situation in Figure 3 may be contrasted with that in Figure 4, where the loops of the $\mathbf{z}$ path do *not* overlap. This is clearly unfavourable for some areas on the sky; e.g. the point $\mathbf{a}'$ is only scanned once in a semester.

Good sky coverage thus requires that the loops of the $\mathbf{z}$ path overlap at least as in Figure 3. Since there is generally a need to minimise the speed of the $\mathbf{z}$ axis on the sky, one should however avoid too much overlap (which would increase the path length and hence the required speed). The minimum path length would be obtained if successive loops just touch as in Figure 5. However, this is not so good either, because the distribution of observation epochs and scan directions would degenerate in an unfavourable way for some points like $\mathbf{a}''$ in Figure 5. A reasonable compromise is to allow a small amount of overlap, as in Figure 3, such that the loops intersect at the ecliptic. If ν is regarded as a function of λ_s (rather than t), it is seen that the condition for having ‘just sufficient’ overlap can be written:

$$\nu(\lambda_{s0} + 2\xi) = 3\pi \quad (6)$$

where λ_{s0} is the initial solar longitude, such that $\nu(\lambda_{s0}) = 0$. A simple form of the revolving scanning law is to make ν increase linearly with λ_s , i.e.:

$$\nu = (\lambda_s - \lambda_{s0})K. \quad (7)$$

In this case the overlap condition, Equation (6), becomes:

$$K = \frac{3\pi}{2\xi} = \frac{270^\circ}{\xi^\circ}. \quad (8)$$

4 The speed of $\mathbf{z}$ on the sky

For the arbitrary law $\nu(t)$ the speed of $\mathbf{z}$ on the sky is found to be:

$$|\dot{\mathbf{z}}| = \left[\left(\dot{\lambda}_s \cos \nu \right)^2 + \left(\dot{\nu} \sin \xi - \dot{\lambda}_s \cos \xi \sin \nu \right)^2 \right]^{1/2}. \quad (9)$$

The eccentricity of the Earth's orbit ($e = 0.0167$) makes $\dot{\lambda}_s$ oscillate by $\pm 1.67\%$ around the mean value $2\pi \text{ rad yr}^{-1}$. If this variation can be neglected, it is more convenient to use λ_s as the 'time' argument of the scanning law. With $S = |\mathbf{dz}/d\lambda_s|$ we have

$$S^2 = \cos^2 \nu + \left(\frac{d\nu}{d\lambda_s} \sin \xi - \cos \xi \sin \nu \right)^2. \quad (10)$$

Now consider the simple law in Equation (7). S is clearly not constant but a mean (actually rms) value is easily calculated since $d\nu/d\lambda_s = K$ and $\langle \sin^2 \nu \rangle = 1/2$:

$$S_{\text{rms}} = \left[1 + \left(K - \frac{1}{2} \right)^2 \sin^2 \xi \right]^{1/2}. \quad (11)$$

Putting $K = 3\pi/2\xi$ gives S_{rms} as function of ξ (Table 1). It is noted that S_{rms} *decreases* slightly with increasing ξ . Thus, perhaps contrary to initial expectations, decreasing the revolving angle (ξ) would not allow a smaller speed of the $\mathbf{z}$ angle on the sky, but quite the opposite: it would require to increase the speed somewhat.

Table 1. Average speed of $\mathbf{z}$ axis on the sky, in units of the speed of the sun, for revolving scanning with $K \equiv d\nu/d\lambda_s = 3\pi/2\xi$.

ξ	K	S_{rms}
30°	9.00	4.366
40°	6.75	4.140
50°	5.40	3.885
60°	4.50	3.606

5 Uniform revolving scanning

If $\nu(\lambda_s)$ is such that S is constant we have what is known as 'uniform revolving scanning'. It is not strictly uniform, because the speed of $\mathbf{z}$ on the sky is $|\dot{\mathbf{z}}| = S\dot{\lambda}_s$, and thus varies by $\pm 1.67\%$ over the year. The function $\nu(\lambda_s)$ may be obtained from the first order differential equation,

$$\frac{d\nu}{d\lambda_s} \sin \xi = (S^2 - \cos^2 \nu)^{1/2} + \cos \xi \sin \nu, \quad (12)$$

for a given value S . For given ξ , the speed S must be adjusted to satisfy the overlap condition Equation (6). This can be checked by setting the initial condition $\nu = 0$ at

$\lambda_s = 0$ and integrating until $\nu = 3\pi$, which should be reached for $\lambda_s = 2\xi$ if S is correct. Table 2 gives this S as a function of ξ for a range of values including the Hipparcos scanning law ($\xi = 43^\circ$) and the feasible range for GAIA. Empirically, the tabular values are accurately fitted by the function

$$S = 0.247 + 4.401 \operatorname{sinc} \xi. \quad (13)$$

Note that the actual maximum speed on the sky is $|\dot{\mathbf{z}}|_{\max} = 1.0167 \times (360^\circ/365.25) \times S = 1.0021S \text{ deg day}^{-1}$. Note also that the values of K and S in Table 2 are *minimum* values for a given ξ , in order to get sufficient overlap of the loops; slightly larger values will give a sky coverage that is just as good, at the expense of a somewhat higher precession speed $|\dot{\mathbf{z}}|$.

Table 2. Speed of $\mathbf{z}$ axis on the sky, in units of the speed of the sun, for uniform revolving scanning satisfying the overlap condition in Equation (6).

ξ	K	S
43°	6.048	4.247
50°	5.220	4.110
51°	5.120	4.089
52°	5.025	4.068
53°	4.933	4.046
54°	4.844	4.025
55°	4.759	4.003
60°	4.377	3.887

6 Coverage during successive years

After a year of revolving scanning the loops in Figure 3 repeat themselves, but generally with a displacement in the revolving phase ν , unless K happens to be an integer. For the best sky uniformity it is desirable to have a certain displacement of the loops from one year to the next, such that the pattern would repeat itself only after T years, if T is the targetted mission length. This condition is satisfied if KT and T are integers with no common divisor greater than 1. For $T = 5$ years this happens for $K = 4.6, 4.8, 5.2$, etc. With $\xi = 55^\circ$, $K = 4.8$ can be realised by increasing S to 4.035; the resulting pattern is shown in Figure 6. Alternatively one could choose $\xi = 54.5^\circ$, which would give almost exactly $K = 4.8$ with the minimum possible $S = 4.014$. With $\xi = 50$ – 51° one can similarly adjust the scanning law to $K = 5.2$. For intermediate angles, $\xi = 52$ – 53° , one would have to avoid the $K = 5$ resonance either by increasing S about 4% (to give $K = 5.2$) or by introducing discontinuities in $\nu(t)$ at suitable intervals. Discontinuities in the scanning law always produce some additional non-uniformity in the sky coverage, and are therefore in principle undesirable. Tentatively, therefore, the best choice of the revolving angle is $\xi = 54.5^\circ$, with $\xi = 50$ – 51° as a possible (but significantly inferior) alternative.

Figure 1. Geometry of parallax measurement: $\mathbf{s}$ = sun, $\mathbf{z}$ = satellite spin axis; $\mathbf{a}$ = star.

Figure 2. Definition of scanning law angles ξ , ν , λ_z and β_z . λ_s is the ecliptic longitude of the sun.

Figure 3. Path of the $\mathbf{z}$ axis on the sky in the revolving scanning law. Observation of the star at $\mathbf{a}$ is possible when the spin axis is at points $\mathbf{z}_1$, $\mathbf{z}_2$ and $\mathbf{z}_3$. A is the great circle with pole at $\mathbf{a}$.

Figure 4. Revolving scanning with insufficient speed of $\mathbf{z}$ on the sky, resulting in non-overlapping loops and a bad coverage e.g. of the point $\mathbf{a}'$. A' is the great circle with pole at $\mathbf{a}'$.

Figure 5. Revolving scanning with touching loops. The coverage of the point $\mathbf{a}''$ partially degenerates to many scans in the same (north–south) direction. A'' is the great circle with pole at $\mathbf{a}''$.

Figure 6. Five years of revolving scanning with $\xi = 55^\circ$ and $K = 4.8$. The path is shown with one dot for each spin period (3 hours).

The scanning law for GAIA (Erratum)

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Equation (11) in SAG.LL.014 is wrong. It should read

$$S_{\text{rms}} = \left[1 + (K^2 - \frac{1}{2}) \sin^2 \xi\right]^{1/2} \quad (11)$$

(cf. Hoyer et al., A&A 101, 228, 1981, Equation A.20). As a consequence, the values in Table 1 are also wrong. The corrected table is given hereafter.

Table 1. Average speed of $\mathbf{z}$ axis on the sky, in units of the speed of the sun, for revolving scanning with $K \equiv d\nu/d\lambda_s = 3\pi/2\xi$.

ξ	K	S_{rms}
30°	9.00	4.596
40°	6.75	4.429
50°	5.40	4.221
60°	4.50	3.976